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Synergistic effects of integrating date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea: an agroecological approach to enhancing tomato growth and soil fertility

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This study investigated the synergistic effects of integrating date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea on soil fertility, microbial activity, and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* "Roma") growth under controlled conditions within an agroecological framework. Five treatments were evaluated: control soil, compost tea, date palm biochar combined with compost tea, compost combined with compost tea, and a combined application of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea. Soil physicochemical properties, enzymatic activities, microbial populations, and plant growth parameters were assessed. The combined application of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea resulted in the most pronounced improvements in soil properties, including a 51.9% increase in organic carbon, a 2.1% increase in total nitrogen, and enhanced cation exchange capacity. Soil enzymatic activities, including β -glucosidase, alkaline phosphatase, and urease, increased significantly, reflecting improved nutrient cycling, while microbial populations (bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes) were also significantly enhanced. These improvements were associated with superior plant performance, as evidenced by higher leaf nitrogen (2.19%), phosphorus (0.53%), and potassium (4.64%) concentrations, increased plant height and stem diameter, greater biomass accumulation, and improved chlorophyll content. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea as sustainable alternatives to conventional fertilizers and provide the first evidence of the synergistic effects of this specific triple-amendment strategy as an integrated agroecological practice for improving soil quality and tomato production. Further research is required to validate these results under field conditions across diverse agroecological systems.

KEYWORDS

date palm biochar, compost, compost tea, soil enzymes, microbial activity, *Solanum lycopersicum*, soil fertility, agroecology

1 Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is one of the most widely cultivated vegetable crops worldwide, playing a vital role in food security and economic development. In Morocco, tomato cultivation is particularly significant, contributing substantially to the national economy through both local consumption and export markets. Major production areas, such as Souss-Massa, support Morocco's standing as one of the leading global exporters of tomatoes (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023). However, maintaining this high productivity has relied heavily on synthetic fertilizers, which pose significant environmental challenges. These include soil degradation, reduced microbial biodiversity, and pollution of water systems through nutrient leaching and greenhouse gas emissions (Benabderrazik et al., 2022; Rhioui et al., 2023). Tackling these challenges requires the adoption of sustainable soil fertility management strategies. Agroecology emphasizes ecosystem-based soil fertility management through the use of organic amendments such as biochar, compost, and compost tea. These materials enhance soil structure, stimulate microbial activity, and promote plant growth while reducing environmental impacts compared to synthetic fertilizers (Sánchez-Monedero, 2019; Merzlaya, 2022; Dapour et al., 2023; Bhattacharyya et al., 2024).

Biochar is a carbon-rich material produced through the pyrolysis of agricultural and agro-industrial organic by-products under limited oxygen conditions (Rehali et al., 2025; Merlin, 2023; Ben Salem et al., 2021). The composition and physicochemical properties of biochar vary depending on the feedstock (e.g., wood, manure, or crop residues) and pyrolysis parameters, which directly influence its effectiveness as a soil amendment (Mishra et al., 2023). With over 6 million date palms, Morocco

produces approximately 200,000 tons of agricultural residues (e.g., fronds, trunks, spathes, fruit stalks) annually. This substantial and currently underexploited biomass represents an abundant, low-cost feedstock that can be valorized through pyrolysis. Its conversion into biochar presents a promising pathway for enabling sustainable agricultural applications within a circular economy framework (Hammani et al., 2020).

Date palm biochar is characterized by high porosity, a stable carbon structure, and a strong capacity for nutrient retention, suggesting it is well-suited for soil improvement and agroecological practices (Rehali et al., 2025; Almutairi et al., 2022; Banitalebi et al., 2019). Its stability allows for long-term carbon sequestration, while its porous structure can enhance soil aeration, water-holding capacity, and microbial activity (Singh et al., 2023; Ndoung et al., 2021). These properties contribute to improved soil fertility and resilience, particularly in arid and semi-arid environments (Wang et al., 2022; Liao et al., 2021; Hale et al., 2021; Alotaibi and Schoenau, 2019; She et al., 2018). In tomato cultivation, biochar has been reported to support plant growth, yield, and resistance to abiotic stresses by optimizing soil conditions and fostering beneficial microbial interactions (Guo et al., 2021; Calcan et al., 2022). Its ability to adsorb and retain essential nutrients, such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K), minimizes leaching losses and ensures their availability for plant uptake, ultimately improving fruit yield and quality (Luigi et al., 2022; Simiele et al., 2022). Additionally, biochar supports nitrogen-fixing bacteria and organic matter decomposition, further enriching soil fertility and promoting sustainable vegetable production (Luigi et al., 2022; Simiele et al., 2022).

Compost, produced through the aerobic decomposition of organic residues, can enrich soil with essential nutrients and beneficial microorganisms (El Kinany et al., 2022; Aguilar-Paredes

et al., 2023). Its application in tomato cropping systems enhances soil aeration, water retention, and nutrient availability, promoting efficient root development and plant growth (Nguyen et al., 2012). Additionally, compost improves fruit quality by increasing sugar content, firmness, and antioxidant levels. Its slow-release mechanism ensures a continuous supply of N, P, and K, supporting sustained crop productivity (Arthur et al., 2012; Durmuş and Kizilkaya, 2022).

Compost tea, a biologically active liquid extract of compost, supplies readily available nutrients and beneficial microorganisms that enhance plant growth and soil health (Garg and Rakshit, 2024). In tomato cultivation, it improves nutrient uptake, stimulates microbial activity, and strengthens plant defenses against pathogens (Li et al., 2024; Bakker et al., 2024). Its application promotes seed germination, root elongation, and enzymatic functions, leading to increased N and P availability. Additionally, compost tea enhances soil microbial diversity, accelerating nutrient mineralization and organic matter decomposition (Abubaker et al., 2024). These benefits contribute to improved soil fertility, higher yields, and superior fruit quality in tomato production (Villego et al., 2020). While individual and paired applications of these organic fertilizers have been widely studied, their combined effects, where the synergy between biochar's structure, compost's nutrients, and compost tea's microbial consortium is explicitly leveraged within an agroecological framework, remain underexplored. Research has shown that integrating biochar and compost, biochar and compost tea, or compost and compost tea, can improve soil physical and chemical properties, enhance nutrient retention, and promote plant growth (Edenborn et al., 2017; Hakim Rabet and Ketabchi, 2021; Qian et al., 2023). For instance, the combination of biochar and compost enhances soil stability and nutrient retention, while compost tea provides an additional boost to microbial activity and nutrient cycling (De Corato, 2020; Ud Din et al., 2023). However, no studies have explored the synergistic effects of applying all three amendments: biochar, compost, and compost tea together. This gap in the literature highlights the need for a comprehensive investigation into their combined potential for improving soil health and plant productivity. This study aimed to evaluate the synergistic effects of biochar, compost, and compost tea on soil health and tomato plant growth under controlled conditions. We investigated the impact of these treatments on soil chemical properties, including organic carbon, total nitrogen, and cation exchange capacity, as well as nutrient uptake and plant growth parameters, such as height, diameter, and biomass. Additionally, this study examined changes in soil enzymatic activity and microbial biomass as indicators of soil fertility.

However, no studies have explored the synergistic effects of applying all three amendments: biochar, compost, and compost tea together. This gap in the literature highlights the need for a comprehensive investigation into their combined potential for improving soil health and plant productivity. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the synergistic effects of biochar, compost, and compost tea on soil health and tomato plant growth under controlled conditions. We investigated the impact of these treatments on soil chemical properties, including organic carbon, total nitrogen, and cation exchange capacity, as well as nutrient uptake and plant growth parameters, such as height,

diameter, and biomass. Additionally, this study examined changes in soil enzymatic activity and microbial biomass as indicators of soil fertility. It was hypothesized that the combination of these organic amendments would enhance nutrient availability and soil biological activity more effectively than their individual or paired applications, providing an agroecological pathway to improve soil fertility and crop performance.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Site description and greenhouse conditions

The experiment was carried out in a greenhouse at the National School of Agriculture of Meknes, Morocco (33°52' N, 5°32' W; altitude 564 m). The greenhouse maintained a controlled temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under natural light throughout the experiment. The sandy soil used in this study was air-dried and sterilized twice in an autoclave at 121°C for 20 min to eliminate microbial contamination and ensure sterility. Its initial physicochemical properties are presented in Table 1. The experiment lasted 12 weeks, during which plants were irrigated regularly to maintain soil moisture near field capacity.

2.2 Experimental design and treatments

Tomato seeds (*Solanum lycopersicum* L., cv. "Roma") were first germinated in seedling trays filled with sterilized soil. Uniform seedlings were transplanted after 25 days into cylindrical plastic pots measuring 19 cm in height, with a base diameter of 15 cm and a top diameter of 20 cm, each containing 6 kg of soil mixed with the designated treatments. A completely randomized design (CRD) was adopted, consisting of five treatments with six replicates each: control soil, compost tea alone (CT), date palm biochar combined with compost tea (BC + CT), compost with compost tea (C + CT), and the combined application of all three amendments (C + BC + CT). Compost tea was applied at a rate of 200 mL per pot every 15 days. Pots were periodically rearranged to minimize positional bias within the greenhouse.

The compost used was a certified organic product (Compost Benchikh, Meknes, Morocco) derived primarily from mixed green waste (vegetable residues) and cattle manure, ensuring a balanced nutrient and microbial composition (C/N = 12.5). The compost tea was prepared from the same compost using an aerated extraction process for 48 h, following the protocol described by OuZine et al. (2022). The different treatment combinations of biochar, compost, and compost tea, along with their respective application rates, are presented in Table 2.

2.3 Preparation and characterization of organic amendments

Three organic amendments, date palm biochar (DPB), compost (C), and compost tea (CT), were used in the experiment. The biochar was produced from date palm residues (DPR), which

TABLE 1 Physicochemical properties of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea, including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), organic matter (OM), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P₂O₅), available potassium (K₂O), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn), organic carbon (C_{org}), and carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C/N).

Treatments	pH	EC (dS/m)	OM (%)	N (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	K ₂ O (%)	Mg (%)	Ca (%)	Fe (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	C _{org} (%)	C/N
Soil	6.4	0.08	0.34	0.02	-	0.028	0.022	8.10	2.06	0.50	0.46	-	0.20	10
Date palm biochar	9.19	2.9	30.8	0.74	0.2	2.1	2.03	5.51	525.9	46	21.2	35.5	70.74	97.1
Compost	9.1	3.7	44.7	1.79	1.4	2.52	1.68	5.26	15,599.4	120	26.7	521.5	22.4	12.5
Compost tea	7.5	4.9	40.7	6.67	3.82	20	2.78	4.67	12,548.3	120	116.7	461.7	20.4	3.1

TABLE 2 Treatment combinations of biochar (BC), compost (C), and compost tea (CT), and their application rates.

Treatments	Biochar (BC)	Compost (C)	Compost tea (CT)
Control	-	-	-
CT	-	-	200 mL/pot/15 days
BC + CT	5% (w/w)	-	200 mL/pot/15 days
C + CT	-	6% (w/w)	200 mL/pot/15 days
BC + C + CT	5% (w/w)	6% (w/w)	200 mL/pot/15 days

were air-dried, crushed (<5 mm), and pyrolyzed in a muffle furnace (Nabertherm L5/11, Germany). The heating rate was set at 10°C min⁻², and the temperature was raised to 500°C and maintained for 4 h before allowing the material to cool naturally. These parameters were chosen based on optimization studies by Rehali et al. (2025), which identified 500°C for 4 h as an optimum condition for date-palm residues. This temperature-time combination maximized carbon stability and aromaticity, improved surface functionality for cation exchange, conserved key nutrients such as P and K, and minimized N loss and tar formation. Thus, it represents the best balance between physicochemical quality and yield for this specific feedstock.

The compost used was a certified organic product (Compost Benchikh, Meknes, Morocco) made from a mixture of green waste and cattle manure with a C/N ratio of 12.5, ensuring a balanced nutrient and microbial composition. Compost tea was prepared from the same compost using an aerated extraction (1:10 w/v compost: water) for 48 h, following the protocol of OuZine et al. (2022). After filtration, the tea was stored at 4°C until use. The detailed physicochemical properties of the three amendments are presented in Table 1.

2.4 Plant cultivation and measurements

After transplanting, plants were maintained under greenhouse conditions for 12 weeks. Agronomic and physiological parameters were recorded weekly.

Plant height was measured using a measuring tape by stretching the plant along with its leaves and recording the distance from the soil surface to the tip of the tallest leaf. The stem diameter of tomato plants was measured weekly using a digital caliper at 2 cm above the soil line to assess variations in stem thickness among treatments. The number of flowers per plant was recorded weekly from the first appearance of buds to the last flowering stage.

After 35 days of tomato seedling transplantation, the chlorophyll content was measured using a SPAD meter (Konica Minolta, Europe). The SPAD value for each leaf was determined by averaging four readings taken from both sides of the leaf's midrib. Throughout the growth period, flowers were counted weekly from the time of emergence until the final week, with buds included

in the count. Ten weeks after planting, plants were harvested, and growth parameters were determined. Roots were carefully uprooted, washed with water, and dried with paper towels before weighing. The fresh weight of roots and shoots was measured using an electronic balance. The samples were then oven-dried at 65°C until they reached a constant weight, after which the dry weight was determined (Ud Din et al., 2023).

2.5 Leaf nutrient concentrations

Leaves of tomato plants were oven-dried at 70°C for 48 h and subsequently ground. The concentrations of phosphorus (P), potassium (K), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu) in the leaves were determined after digestion with H₂SO₄-H₂O₂, following the method described by Parkinson and Allen (1975). The digests were analyzed for Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). The total potassium content was measured with a flame photometer (Johnston et al., 1952). Phosphorus content was determined colorimetrically using a spectrophotometer, as described by Allen et al. (1976). Boron (B) was quantified by dry ashing (Pratt and Chapman, 1961) and subsequently measured by colorimetry using azomethine H (Bingham, 1982).

2.6 Soil sampling and analyses

2.6.1 Physico-chemical analysis

Soil samples were collected from each treatment at the start of the experiment and again at the end of the growing season to evaluate changes in soil composition resulting from the applied treatments.

Physico-chemical analyses were conducted to measure key soil properties. The pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were assessed using a 1:5 soil/distilled water (w/v) suspension, employing pre-calibrated pH and EC meters (Staff of USSL, 1954). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined from the concentrations of exchangeable cations (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺) according to the protocol described by Graber et al. (2017). Organic matter and organic carbon were quantified via wet acid-sulfate digestion following the Walkley and Black (1934) method. Total nitrogen (Nt) and phosphorus (P) concentrations were determined using the Kjeldahl technique and the Olsen extraction method, respectively, followed by spectrophotometric analysis (Kjeldahl, 1883; Olsen, 1954). Potassium (K), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), and zinc (Zn) were analyzed using atomic absorption spectroscopy. The percentage of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃%) was assessed using the Bernard method. Mechanical analysis was conducted for the soil samples to estimate soil texture using the hydrometer method (Gee and Bauder, 1986).

2.6.2 Soil enzymatic activities

Soil samples were analyzed for their β-glucosidase activity by incubating soil samples with p-nitrophenyl-β-D-glucopyranoside

in a buffered solution at 37°C for 1 h. The amount of p-nitrophenol released was quantified colorimetrically, indicating the soil's capacity to decompose organic matter (Naseby and Lynch, 1997). Alkaline phosphatase activity using a calorimetric estimation of the p-nitrophenol released by phosphatase activity when soil is incubated with buffered (pH 6.5) sodium p-nitrophenyl phosphate solution and toluene at 37°C for 1 h (Tabatabai and Bremner, 1969). Urease activity which involves the determination of the ammonium released by incubation of the soil sample (5 g) with tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, urea solution and toluene (0–2 mL) at 37°C for 2 h (Zantua and Bremner, 1975). All determinations of enzymatic activities were performed in triplicate, and all values reported are averages of the three determinations expressed on an oven-dried soil basis (105°C).

2.6.3 Microbial load

At the end of the growth cycle, soil microbial load was evaluated using the dilution suspension technique, as described by Yan et al. (2015). Ten grams of soil were suspended in 90 mL of sterile water to prepare a 10⁻² dilution. Serial dilutions were then performed by transferring 1 mL of the initial suspension to 9 mL of sterile water, continuing this process to achieve the desired dilution levels. The diluted samples were plated on nutrient agar (NA) for bacteria, potato dextrose agar (PDA) supplemented with 50 mg/L chloramphenicol for fungi, and actinomycete isolation agar (AIA) for actinomycetes. Plates were incubated at 30°C for 24–48 h for bacteria, 25°C for 3–5 days for fungi, and 28°C for 5–7 days for actinomycetes. After incubation, colonies were counted, and the colony-forming units (CFU) per gram of soil were calculated.

2.7 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in SPSS software (Version 27, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). When differences were significant, Tukey's HSD test at a *p* < 0.05 confidence level was carried out. This analysis was applied to all soil and plant parameters measured at the end of the experiment.

Additionally, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using XLSTAT to explore relationships among variables and identify the most influential parameters contributing to the observed effects of treatments. The PCA results complemented the ANOVA findings, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the synergistic impacts of the applied amendments.

3 Results

3.1 Agronomic growth parameters

Plant agronomic parameters varied significantly among treatments. Plant height varied significantly among treatments according to the ANOVA test (*p* < 0.05). The control treatment recorded the lowest average height (41.51 cm), while CT increased it to 56.77 cm. The BC + CT and C + CT treatments resulted in further increases, reaching 68.80 cm and 69.33 cm, respectively.

The highest average plant height (72.03 cm) was obtained under the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT). Pairwise comparison using Tukey's HSD test indicated that the difference between C + CT and C + BC + CT was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), whereas both treatments produced plants significantly taller than the control and CT ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1A).

Plant stem diameter followed a similar trend to plant height treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control exhibited the lowest mean diameter (4.83 mm). The CT application resulted in an increased diameter, reaching 5.20 mm, whereas BC + CT reached 7 mm. The compost combined with compost tea treatment (C + CT) showed a further increase to 9.22 mm. The highest mean diameter (12.35 mm) was obtained under the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT), which was significantly different from all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1B).

The number of leaves per plant, an important indicator of plant health and vigor, also varied significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment exhibited the lowest mean leaf count (4.83 leaves per plant). Application of compost tea (CT) increased the average to 6.50 leaves, while the combination of biochar and compost tea (BC + CT) reached 7 leaves. The compost combined with compost tea (C + CT) treatment further increased the mean number to 12.67 leaves. The highest average leaf number (14.67 leaves per plant) was recorded in the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT), which was significantly higher than all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1C).

The number of flowers per plant, a critical indicator of reproductive potential, differed significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment produced no flowers, while the compost tea (CT) treatment showed a slight increase with an average of 0.34 flowers per plant. The biochar combined with compost tea (BC + CT) treatment resulted in 3.33 flowers per plant. The compost combined with compost tea (C + CT) treatment exhibited a higher mean value of 9.17 flowers per plant. The combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) recorded the highest average (11 flowers per plant), which was significantly different from the other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1D).

Chlorophyll content, expressed as SPAD value, varied significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment exhibited the lowest mean chlorophyll value (22.40). Application of compost tea (CT) increased chlorophyll content to 24.47, while the combination of biochar and compost tea (BC + CT) further increased it to 27.18. The compost combined with compost tea (C + CT) treatment showed a significant rise, reaching 43.80, whereas the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) recorded the highest average chlorophyll content (48.91), which was significantly different from all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1E).

Shoot fresh and dry weights varied significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment recorded the lowest fresh weight (17.89 g per plant). The compost tea (CT) treatment increased the value to 21.15 g, while the combination of biochar and compost tea (BC + CT) resulted in 22.79 g. The compost combined

with compost tea (C + CT) treatment showed a marked increase to 55.21 g, and the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) recorded the highest fresh weight (64.49 g), which was significantly different from all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Dry biomass followed a similar statistical trend ($p < 0.05$). The control (T-) exhibited the lowest dry weight (1.48 g), followed by CT (2.45 g), BC + CT (3.34 g), and C + CT (8.23 g). The highest dry biomass was obtained under the C + BC + CT treatment (12.45 g), which differed significantly from all other treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 2A).

Root fresh and dry weights differed significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment showed the lowest mean fresh root weight (22.76 g per plant). The compost tea (CT) treatment increased this value to 32.72 g, while the combination of biochar and compost tea (BC + CT) and compost with compost tea (C + CT) further increased fresh root weight to 40.44 g and 64.76 g, respectively. The highest mean fresh root weight (73.24 g) was obtained under the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT), which was significantly higher than all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Dry root weight followed a similar statistical trend ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment averaged 8.61 g per plant, while CT increased it to 12.30 g. The BC + CT and C + CT treatments achieved 14.89 g and 26.54 g, respectively. The combined treatment (C + BC + CT) recorded the highest dry root weight (29.11 g), which differed significantly from all other treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 2B).

3.2 Leaf nutrient content

The nutrient concentrations in tomato leaves varied significantly across treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). The control treatment exhibited the lowest nutrient levels, with nitrogen (0.77%), phosphorus (0.11%), and potassium (1.95%), along with lower concentrations of magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), and micronutrients. The compost tea (CT) treatment increased nutrient concentrations to 1.60% N, 0.40% P, and 2.98% K. The biochar and compost tea combination (BC + CT) further improved these values, reaching 2.16% N, 0.53% P, and 3.64% K. The compost with compost tea treatment (C + CT) recorded 1.96% N, 0.43% P, and 3.45% K, along with a magnesium concentration of 1.26% and boron (B) content of 56 mg kg⁻¹.

The combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) consistently recorded the highest nutrient concentrations, with 2.19% N, 0.39% P, and 4.64% K. In addition, this treatment exhibited elevated levels of Mg (1.35%), Ca (2.96%), and Fe (369 mg kg⁻¹), as well as higher concentrations of Zn (18 mg kg⁻¹), Cu (4.9 mg kg⁻¹), Mn (67 mg kg⁻¹), and B (67 mg kg⁻¹). All increases were statistically significant compared with the control. The control treatment exhibited the lowest nutrient levels, with nitrogen (0.77%), phosphorus (0.11%), and potassium (1.95%), along with lower concentrations of magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), and micronutrients. The compost tea (CT) treatment increased nutrient concentrations to 1.60% N, 0.40% P, and 2.98% K. The biochar and compost tea combination (BC + CT) further improved these values, reaching 2.16% N, 0.53% P, and 3.64% K. The compost

FIGURE 1 Agronomic parameters of tomato plants under different treatments. The parameters include: **(A)** plant height (cm), **(B)** stem diameter (mm), **(C)** number of leaves (No. per plant), **(D)** number of flowers (No. per plant), **(E)** chlorophyll content (SPAD value). Treatments: Control, CT (Compost Tea), BC + CT (Biochar + Compost Tea), C + CT (Compost + Compost Tea), and C + BC + CT (Compost + Biochar + Compost Tea). Values are presented as means ± standard deviations ($n = 6$). Different letters (a–d) above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments, as determined by Tukey’s *post hoc* test at $p < 0.05$. Bars sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

FIGURE 2 Fresh and dry biomass of tomato plants under different treatments. The parameters measured include **(A)** fresh and dry weights of the aerial parts and **(B)** fresh and dry weights of the root systems. Fresh weights are represented by blue bars, and dry weights are represented by orange bars. Control, CT (Compost Tea), BC + CT (Biochar + Compost Tea), C + CT (Compost + Compost Tea), and C + BC + CT (Compost + Biochar + Compost Tea). Different letters (a–d) and (a'–d') above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments within each measured parameter, as determined by Tukey’s *post hoc* test at $p < 0.05$. Letters a–d refer to fresh biomass, while letters a'–d' refer to dry biomass. Bars sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

TABLE 3 Macronutrient and micronutrient content in the tomato leaves under different treatments: control, CT (compost tea), BC + CT (biochar + compost tea), C + CT (compost + compost tea), and C + BC + CT (compost + biochar + compost tea).

Treatments	N (%)	P (%)	K (%)	Mg (%)	Ca (%)	Zn (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	B (mg/kg)
Control	0.77 ± 0.02d	0.11 ± 0.01d	1.95 ± 0.12d	0.88 ± 0.05d	1.32 ± 0.08d	14 ± 0.8c	2.22 ± 0.1d	55 ± 2.5c	94 ± 3.5d	32 ± 1.6d
CT	1.6 ± 0.05c	0.4 ± 0.02c	2.98 ± 0.15c	1.08 ± 0.07c	2.89 ± 0.12a	21 ± 1.0b	4.8 ± 0.2b	166 ± 4.2a	193 ± 3.31c	43 ± 2.1c
BC + CT	2.16 ± 0.04a	0.53 ± 0.03a	3.64 ± 0.21b	1 ± 0.05c	2.55 ± 0.11b	22 ± 1.15a	5.6 ± 0.3a	80 ± 2.84b	123 ± 3.5d	48 ± 2.4b
C + CT	1.96 ± 0.03b	0.43 ± 0.02b	3.45 ± 0.18b	1.26 ± 0.06b	2.37 ± 0.23c	20 ± 1.14b	3.4 ± 0.2c	78 ± 2.77b	160 ± 4.02c	56 ± 2.7a
C + BC + CT	2.19 ± 0.05a	0.39 ± 0.02b	4.64 ± 0.22a	1.35 ± 0.07a	2.96 ± 0.13a	18 ± 0.98c	4.9 ± 0.3b	67 ± 2.2b	369 ± 6.5a	67 ± 3.3a

Values are expressed as means ± standard deviations ($n = 4$). Different letters within a column indicate significant differences (Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.05$). N, Total Nitrogen; P, Phosphorus; K, Potassium; Mg, Magnesium; Ca, Calcium; Zn, Zinc; Cu, Copper; Mn, Manganese; Fe, Iron; B, Boron.

with compost tea treatment (C + CT) recorded 1.96% N, 0.43% P, and 3.45% K, along with a magnesium concentration of 1.26% and boron (B) content of 56 mg kg⁻¹.

The combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) consistently recorded the highest nutrient concentrations, with 2.19% N, 0.39% P, and 4.64% K. In addition, this treatment exhibited elevated levels of Mg (1.35%), Ca (2.96%), and Fe (369 mg kg⁻¹), as well as higher concentrations of Zn (18 mg kg⁻¹), Cu (4.9 mg kg⁻¹), Mn (67 mg kg⁻¹), and B (67 mg kg⁻¹). All increases were statistically significant compared with the control. These results highlight the enhanced nutrient absorption and availability induced by the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea amendments.

3.3 Effect of organic amendments on soil characteristics

3.3.1 Physico-chemical characteristics

The results of the soil analyses reveal significant changes in soil chemical properties, depending on the applied treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

At the beginning of the experiment, the soils of the different treatments exhibited the following characteristics: organic carbon (Corg) was the lowest in the control treatment at 0.5%. In comparison, it was slightly higher in the CT treatment at 0.9%. It was significantly higher in the BC + CTi and C + BC + CTi treatments, reaching 2.9% and 14.4%, respectively. Nt was also lowest in T- at 0.08%, increased slightly in CT to 0.12%, and was significantly higher in BC + CTi and C + BC + CTi at 1.73% and 1.74%, respectively. CEC and EC were also notably higher in C + CTi and C + BC + CTi, showing enhanced soil chemical status prior to plant growth and better nutrient retention in these soils.

At the end of the experiment, all treatments showed a significant increase in organic carbon content ($p < 0.05$). The highest Corg values were observed in C + CTf (23.6%) and C + BC + CTf (32%). Nt increased across treatments, with a maximum value of 2.1% in the C + BC + CTf treatment. CEC also improved significantly, reflecting a better ability of the soil to retain nutrients, particularly in BC + CTf and C + BC + CTf. EC increased in all

treatments, with the highest values recorded in the C + BC + CTf treatment, reflecting higher levels of soluble ions in the soil after the application of organic amendments ($p < 0.05$).

3.3.2 Soil enzymatic activity

Soil enzymatic activities, an indicator of soil health and nutrient cycling, showed significant variations across treatments ($p < 0.05$). The activities of β -glucosidase, alkaline phosphatase, and urease were measured to assess carbon, phosphorus, and nitrogen cycles, respectively (Figure 3).

β -glucosidase activity, which is important for organic matter decomposition and the carbon cycle, was lowest in the control treatment (0.059 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$). The compost tea (CT) treatment significantly increased activity to 0.89 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$, while the biochar combined with compost tea (BC + CT) treatment reached 1.87 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$. The compost with compost tea (C + CT) treatment showed an intermediate value of 0.98 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$, whereas the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT) recorded the highest β -glucosidase activity (2.74 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$), significantly higher than all other treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3A).

Alkaline phosphatase activity is an indicator of the phosphorus cycle, also varied significantly across treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment had the lowest activity (0.79 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$), followed by CT (2.26 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$). The BC + CT and C + CT treatments reached 12.96 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$ and 20.44 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$, respectively. The C + BC + CT treatment showed the highest activity (28.08 $\mu\text{mol PNP g}^{-1}$), which was significantly greater than all other treatments according to Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3B).

Urease activity, which is critical for N transformation, was also lowest in the control treatment at 0.039 $\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+/\text{g}$. CT showed a moderate improvement to 0.31 $\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+/\text{g}$. BC + CT further enhanced urease activity to 1.19 $\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+/\text{g}$, while C + CT achieved 2.90 $\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+/\text{g}$. The highest urease activity was observed in the C + BC + CT treatment at 5.28 $\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+/\text{g}$, highlighting significantly improved N availability in soils treated with combined organic amendments (Figure 3C).

Urease activity, which is critical for N transformation, followed the same statistical pattern ($p < 0.05$). The control recorded the

TABLE 4 Initial and final soil chemical properties across treatments: control, CT (compost tea), BC + CT (biochar + compost tea), C + CT (compost + compost tea), and C + BC + CT (compost + biochar + compost tea).

Experiment stage	Treatment	Corg (%)	OM (%)	Nt (%)	N-NO ₃ (mg/kg)	Ca (cmol/kg)	CEC (cmol/kg)	EC (dS/m)	Cu (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	P (mg/kg)	K ₂ O (mg/kg)
Initialcontent	Control i	0.5 ± 0.02d	0.9 ± 0.05d	0.08 ± 0.01d	10 ± 0.98d	0.2 ± 0.05d	0.4 ± 0.02d	0.1 ± 0.05c	0.02 ± 0.001d	0.03 ± 0.002d	0.3 ± 0.001d	0.9 ± 0.003d	5 ± 0.1d	0.02 ± 0.002d
	CTi	0.9 ± 0.03c	1.5 ± 0.9c	0.12 ± 0.09c	24.6 ± 1.11c	2.3 ± 0.61b	0.9 ± 0.05c	0.113 ± 0.35c	0.11 ± 0.01c	0.1 ± 0.01c	4.99 ± 0.95c	1.18 ± 0.11c	14.4 ± 1.36c	0.03 ± 0.008c
	BC + CTi	14.4 ± 1.01a	24.8 ± 2.33a	1.73 ± 0.05a	21.5 ± 1.02c	1.6 ± 0.18c	2 ± 0.15a	0.155 ± 0.09b	0.16 ± 0.05b	0.19 ± 0.04b	2.29 ± 0.88c	1.05 ± 0.13c	35 ± 1.54b	0.14 ± 0.02b
	C + CTi	2.9 ± 0.68b	5 ± 0.23b	0.43 ± 0.05b	18.7 ± 1.01c	2.3 ± 0.19b	2 ± 0.05a	0.484 ± 0.01a	0.32 ± 0.05a	2.17 ± 0.73a	3.73 ± 0.53b	10.6 ± 0.99b	114 ± 2.88a	0.94 ± 0.02a
	C + BC + CTi	14.4 ± 1.53a	25.5 ± 0.99a	1.74 ± 0.05a	20.5 ± 0.98c	2.3 ± 0.01b	2.1 ± 0.19a	0.428 ± 0.04a	0.26 ± 0.02a	1.56 ± 0.58a	3.71 ± 0.41b	7.35 ± 0.23b	111 ± 2.56a	1.17 ± 0.01a
Finalcontent	Control f	0.2 ± 0.01e	0.4 ± 0.05e	0.02 ± 0.001d	9 ± 0.1c	0.1 ± 0.03d	0.29 ± 0.01d	0.09 ± 0.01d	0.19 ± 0.05c	0.06 ± 0.005d	0.6 ± 0.056d	0.83 ± 0.09d	3.5 ± 0.99e	0.01 ± 0.009e
	CTf	1.2 ± 0.05d	2.1 ± 0.05d	0.16 ± 0.02c	21.4 ± 1.05b	1.4 ± 0.09c	2.6 ± 0.01c	0.99 ± 0.01c	0.01 ± 0.009d	0.05 ± 0.001d	1.67 ± 0.21c	1.67 ± 0.23c	30.8 ± 1.55d	0.03 ± 0.02d
	BC + CTf	17.8 ± 1.45b	30.6 ± 2.01b	1.84 ± 0.05b	21.4 ± 1.99b	2 ± 0.01b	2.3 ± 0.12c	0.168 ± 0.03d	0.11 ± 0.03c	0.23 ± 0.01c	3.15 ± 0.15b	1.5 ± 0.19c	53.1 ± 2.88c	0.61 ± 0.2b
	C + CTf	23.6 ± 0.59b	26.2 ± 1.02c	0.5 ± 0.02c	19.8 ± 0.18b	2.1 ± 0.3b	2.1 ± 0.45c	0.127 ± 0.06d	0.16 ± 0.6c	0.94 ± 0.1b	3.32 ± 0.5b	5.59 ± 0.97b	102 ± 2.17b	0.25 ± 0.01c
	C + BC + CTf	32 ± 0.4a	51.9 ± 2.12a	2.1 ± 0.2a	18.3 ± 0.5b	1.8 ± 0.05c	1.8 ± 0.3c	0.517 ± 0.05b	0.30 ± 0.22b	1.31 ± 0.53a	2.53 ± 0.12c	6.55 ± 1.02a	209 ± 3.91a	1.49 ± 0.02a

Values are expressed as means ± standard deviations ($n = 4$). Different letters within a column indicate significant differences (Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.05$). Corg, Organic Carbon; OM, Organic Matter; Nt, Total Nitrogen; N-NO₃, Nitrate Nitrogen; Ca, Calcium; CEC, Cation Exchange Capacity; EC, Electrical Conductivity; Cu, Copper; Zn, Zinc; Mg, Magnesium; Fe, Iron; P, Phosphorus; K₂O, Potassium Oxide.

FIGURE 3

Soil enzymatic activities under different treatments. The enzymatic parameters include: (A) β -glucosidase activity ($\mu\text{mol PNP h}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$), (B) alkaline phosphatase activity ($\mu\text{mol PNP h}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$), and (C) urease activity ($\mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{h}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$). Control, CT (Compost Tea), BC + CT (Biochar + Compost Tea), C + CT (Compost + Compost Tea), and C + BC + CT (Compost + Biochar + Compost Tea). Values are presented as means \pm standard deviations ($n = 6$). Different letters (a–e) above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments, as determined by Tukey's *post hoc* test at $p < 0.05$. Bars sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

lowest activity ($0.039 \mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{g}^{-1}$), while CT increased it to $0.31 \mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{g}^{-1}$. The BC + CT and C + CT treatments achieved $1.19 \mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{g}^{-1}$ and $2.90 \mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. The highest urease activity ($5.28 \mu\text{mol NH}_4^+ \text{g}^{-1}$) was observed in the C + BC + CT treatment, significantly different from all other treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3C).

These results indicate that the combined application of biochar, compost, and compost tea (C + BC + CT) consistently promoted the highest enzymatic activities, underscoring its effectiveness in enhancing soil biological functioning and nutrient cycling.

3.3.3 Microbial load

Figure 4 presents the microbial load in the soil, measured as colony-forming units (CFU) of bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, which exhibited significant variations across treatments ($p < 0.05$).

Bacterial load was lowest in the control treatment ($3.33 \times 10^3 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$). The compost tea (CT) treatment increased bacterial counts to $5.77 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, while the biochar with compost tea (BC + CT) and compost with compost tea (C + CT) treatments further increased bacterial abundance to $1.59 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ and $1.18 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, respectively. The highest bacterial population was recorded in the combined biochar, compost, and compost tea treatment (C + BC + CT), with $7.74 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, which was significantly higher than all other treatments according to the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Fungal populations also showed significant differences among treatments ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment exhibited the lowest fungal count ($2.00 \times 10^3 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$), while CT increased this value to $1.69 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$. The BC + CT and C + CT treatments recorded $2.10 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ and $3.10 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, respectively. The highest fungal population was observed in the C + BC + CT treatment ($7.46 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$), significantly higher than all other treatments ($p < 0.05$).

The actinomycete population followed a similar trend. The lowest load was observed in T- at $2.00 \times 10^3 \text{ CFU}$, while CT improved this to $1.69 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU}$. BC + CT and C + CT reached $6.37 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU}$ and $3.82 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU}$, respectively. The highest actinomycete load was recorded in C + BC + CT at $1.99 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU}$, suggesting enhanced soil health and decomposition processes, indicating better conditions for actinomycete proliferation and organic matter decomposition.

Actinomycete populations followed a similar statistical trend ($p < 0.05$). The control treatment recorded $2.00 \times 10^3 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, while CT increased it to $1.69 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$. The BC + CT and C + CT treatments reached $6.37 \times 10^7 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ and $3.82 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$, respectively. The highest actinomycete population was obtained in the C + BC + CT treatment ($1.99 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$), which differed significantly from all other treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 4).

The results demonstrate that the combination of biochar, compost, and compost tea (C + BC + CT) consistently resulted in the highest microbial abundance across all categories, suggesting

FIGURE 4

Microbial populations in the soil under different treatments. The microbial groups measured include fungi, bacteria, and actinomycetes, represented as log CFU g⁻¹. Control, CT (Compost Tea), BC + CT (Biochar + Compost Tea), C + CT (Compost + Compost Tea), and C + BC + CT (Compost + Biochar + Compost Tea). Values are presented as means \pm standard deviations ($n = 6$). Different letters (a-d), (a'-e'), and (a''-e'') above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments within each microbial group, as determined by Tukey's *post hoc* test at $p < 0.05$. Letters a-d correspond to fungi, letters a'-e' correspond to bacteria, and letters a''-e'' correspond to actinomycetes. Bars sharing the same letter within a given microbial group are not significantly different.

its potential to enhance soil fertility, biological health, and nutrient cycling. The significant increase in fungal populations is consistent with accelerated decomposition of organic matter, leading to enhanced soil structure, nutrient availability, and long-term soil fertility. Likewise, the remarkable growth in actinomycetes, known for their role in organic matter breakdown and natural antibiotic production, highlights a positive shift in microbial communities toward greater soil health and disease suppression potential. Bacterial populations, while varying across treatments, exhibited notable differences, with the C + BC + CT treatment showing the highest bacterial abundance, indicating that the combined amendments may provide a favorable environment for microbial proliferation.

3.4 Interactions between soil properties, tomato growth parameters, and treatment effects

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA), presented in Figure 5, revealed clear correlations among soil physicochemical properties, enzymatic activities, microbial populations, and plant growth parameters. The first two components (F1 and F2) explained 88.54% of the total variance, with F1 (74.21%) representing the dominant axis and F2 (14.33%) capturing secondary variation, indicating strong interdependence among the studied variables.

Key soil fertility indicators, including organic carbon (C_{org}), total nitrogen (N_t), available phosphorus (P), potassium (K₂O), cation exchange capacity (CEC), and electrical conductivity (EC), exhibited high positive loadings on the F1 axis. These were tightly associated with enzymatic activities, including β -glucosidase, urease, and alkaline phosphatase, reflecting enhanced nutrient cycling and organic-matter decomposition under the combined treatment. Such enzymatic processes are critical for transforming

complex organic matter into plant-available nutrients, thereby supporting microbial proliferation and nutrient-rich soils.

The microbial load, represented by bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, was strongly correlated with soil fertility parameters and enzymatic activities, emphasizing the role of microbial communities in nutrient mineralization and overall soil health. Specifically, the C + BC + CT treatment showed a remarkable increase in microbial populations and enzymatic activity, which contributed to higher levels of N and phosphorus in the soil, thereby boosting plant growth. This was further evidenced by the clustering of agronomic parameters such as plant height, diameter, number of leaves and flowers, chlorophyll content, and fresh and dry biomass of aerial and root parts, closely with soil fertility and microbial indicators on the PCA biplot. These agronomic parameters benefited significantly from the enhanced availability of macro- and micronutrients facilitated by the enzymatic activity and microbial dynamics.

The strong alignment of plant growth parameters with soil fertility indicators and microbial activity on the positive F1 axis indicated that the C + BC + CT treatment was the most effective in promoting soil and plant health. This integrated application maximized the synergistic effects of the amendments by improving soil structure, nutrient retention, and microbial symbiosis, leading to superior plant growth and productivity. The enhanced nutrient concentrations in leaves, particularly N, P, K, and Mg, further validated the effectiveness of this treatment in improving nutrient uptake and photosynthetic capacity, as reflected in the increased chlorophyll content.

The C + BC + CT treatment was positioned on the positive side of the F1 axis, clustering with high values of soil fertility, enzymatic activities, microbial load, and plant growth traits. This reflects its cumulative effect of the combined organic amendments in improving soil biochemical functioning and promoting vigorous plant development. Intermediate positions were occupied by BC + CT and C + CT treatments, while the control was located

on the negative side of F1, characterized by poor fertility, weak enzymatic activity, and limited growth. Along the F2 axis, EC and available phosphorus contributed most to treatment separation, indicating secondary variation related to ion-exchange capacity and nutrient solubility.

In contrast, the control treatment was located on the negative side of the F1 axis, indicating minimal contributions to soil fertility, enzymatic activity, microbial diversity, or plant growth. The CT and BC + CT treatments showed intermediate performance, confirming the additive benefits of combining multiple organic amendments. Overall, the PCA analysis demonstrates that soil biochemical parameters, particularly Corg, Nt, and enzymatic activities, were the primary factors influencing microbial abundance and agronomic performance. Treatments that enhanced these soil attributes, notably C + BC + CT, were associated with superior plant growth and nutrient accumulation, confirming the strong interdependence between soil fertility, biological activity, and crop productivity while supporting ecological balance in agroecosystems.

4 Discussion

This study provides valuable insights into the effects of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea, both individually and in combination, on soil fertility, enzymatic activity, microbial populations, and tomato plant growth. The integration of these organic amendments resulted in significant improvements in soil health indicators and plant performance, reinforcing their potential for sustainable agroecological practices.

A key contribution of this study lies in its emphasis on the integrated application of three organic amendments: biochar, compost, and compost tea, derived from locally available date palm residues. While previous research has often explored the individual effects of biochar or compost, the combined use of these amendments has rarely been investigated, particularly when the biochar originates from date palm biomass. This work therefore provides new empirical evidence of the cumulative impact of these amendments on soil biochemical functioning and plant performance under controlled greenhouse conditions.

The effectiveness of biochar lies in its physical and chemical properties. Its porous structure and high surface area enhanced soil organic carbon and cation exchange capacity (CEC), potentially creating a stable reservoir for nutrients and reducing nutrient leaching (Glaser et al., 2002; Lehmann et al., 2003; Kongthod et al., 2015). This effect was evident in the improved N retention observed in biochar-treated soils, reflected in the increased N concentration (2.19%) in tomato leaves. Additionally, biochar's ability to improve soil structure and water retention created an optimal environment for microbial activity and root development (Xing-hua and Jian-wei, 2014); as evidenced by the increased activities of β -glucosidase and urease in biochar-amended soils (Amoakwah et al., 2022). These findings align with the work of Lehmann et al. (2011), highlighting biochar's dual role in nutrient cycling and organic matter stabilization (Rondon et al., 2007). Nevertheless, the date palm biochar used exhibited a high C/N ratio (97.1), which can potentially induce N immobilization by soil microbes, thereby temporarily reducing N availability to plants (Wang et al., 2022). In our experiment, this effect appeared to be mitigated by the co-application of compost (C/N = 12.5) and compost tea, both rich in labile carbon and readily available N. This complementary balance

between labile and recalcitrant carbon sources likely maintained N availability and enhanced plant uptake. The combination may have provided an immediate nutrient source for microbial activity, meeting their initial demand and enabling the long-term benefits of biochar, such as improved cation exchange capacity and habitat formation, to manifest without causing short-term N depletion in tomato plants.

The initial pH of the date palm biochar and compost was high (>9). However, their combined application with near-neutral compost tea (pH 7.5) helped buffer soil alkalinity during the experiment, as this liquid amendment can facilitate short-term pH moderation in the rhizosphere (González-Hernández et al., 2023). Furthermore, the long-term risk of alkalinity is mitigated by the natural “aging” of biochar in soil, a process where surface oxidation forms acidic functional groups that can lower pH over time (Yadav et al., 2019). In fact, alkaline biochar has been shown to have a neutral or even acidifying effect in neutral-to-alkaline soils (Yao et al., 2025). As a precautionary measure in pH-sensitive systems, integrating these amendments with acidic organic inputs or acidifying crop rotations is recommended to maintain optimal soil pH (Qayyum et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2025).

Compost likely contributed to these effects by supplying readily available nutrients, including N, P, and K, which were directly linked to higher nutrient concentrations in plant tissues (Chan et al., 2007). Its high organic matter content can serve as an energy source for soil microbial populations, enhancing enzymatic activities such as alkaline phosphatase, crucial for phosphorus cycling (Liu et al., 2022). Compost also improved soil aggregation and water retention, fostering root penetration and nutrient uptake. These effects were particularly notable in treatments involving both compost and biochar, where plant height, leaf count, and biomass showed marked improvement (Schulz and Glaser, 2012). These results confirm the role of compost as a cornerstone of soil fertility management, as documented by Bernal et al. (2009).

Compost tea, which serves as a concentrated nutrient solution and microbial inoculant, appeared to stimulate microbial activity within the rhizosphere. Its application was correlated with increased abundance of bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, significantly contributing to enzymatic processes critical for nutrient cycling (Ingham, 2005; Pant et al., 2012). For instance, β -glucosidase and urease activities were markedly higher in compost tea-amended soils, indicating improved carbon and N cycling (Amoakwah et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2021). Additionally, the soluble nutrients in compost tea provided an immediate source of nutrition, complementing the slower nutrient release from biochar and compost. This dual action supported sustained plant growth and health, consistent with findings by De Corato (2020) and Pant et al. (2012).

The combined application of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea (C + BC + CT) delivered the most pronounced improvements across all parameters. Organic carbon levels increased by 32%, while Nt reached 2.1%, confirming the cumulative effect of these amendments on soil fertility, as is reported in previous studies using similar amendments (Çig et al., 2021; Xiu et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). Enhanced microbial diversity and enzymatic functions (Lehmann et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2022), coupled with improved soil structure

and nutrient availability, resulted in higher plant chlorophyll content, photosynthetic capacity, and biomass. These outcomes emphasize the complementary roles of biochar, compost, and compost tea in optimizing soil health and plant productivity. Furthermore, the increased concentrations of micronutrients such as zinc, copper, and boron in plant tissues indicate a more balanced and enriched nutritional profile, supporting robust plant growth (Joseph et al., 2018). The combination of compost and compost tea also enriched the soil with soluble nutrients and active microbial populations that enhanced organic matter decomposition and nutrient solubilization. Microorganisms from compost tea, including *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* species, are known to release organic acids that mobilize phosphorus and potassium bound to biochar surfaces. These biogeochemical interactions could explain the pronounced increases in leaf nutrient concentrations, particularly potassium (4.64%) and phosphorus (0.53%), in the C + BC + CT treatment. Enhanced root development and increased urease and phosphatase activities further indicate improved N and P cycling, supporting vigorous plant growth and chlorophyll synthesis (Xing-hua and Jian-wei, 2014; Muhammad et al., 2022).

The combined application of date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea (C + BC + CT) delivered the most pronounced improvements across all measured parameters. Soil organic carbon increased by 32%, and Nt reached 2.1%, confirming the cumulative enhancement of soil fertility previously reported for similar amendment combinations (Çig et al., 2021; Xiu et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). Enhanced microbial diversity and enzymatic activity (Lehmann et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2021), together with improved soil structure and nutrient availability, resulted in higher chlorophyll content, photosynthetic efficiency, and biomass accumulation. These outcomes emphasize the complementary roles of biochar, compost, and compost tea in promoting soil health and plant productivity.

In addition, elevated concentrations of micronutrients such as zinc, copper, and boron in plant tissues indicate a more balanced and enriched nutritional profile, supporting vigorous plant growth (Joseph et al., 2018). The joint application of compost and compost tea enriched the soil with soluble nutrients and metabolically active microbes that accelerated organic matter decomposition and nutrient solubilization. Beneficial microorganisms from compost tea, including *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* spp., release organic acids capable of mobilizing phosphorus and potassium bound to biochar surfaces. These biogeochemical interactions likely account for the marked increases in leaf potassium (4.64%) and phosphorus (0.53%) concentrations observed under the C + BC + CT treatment. Enhanced root development, coupled with elevated urease and phosphatase activities, further supports improved N and P cycling, leading to vigorous vegetative growth and sustained chlorophyll synthesis (Sharma et al., 2017).

The observed improvements in plant growth parameters, including height, diameter, leaf number, and biomass, emphasize the amendments' role in enhancing photosynthetic efficiency and overall plant vigor. Higher magnesium and calcium concentrations in plant tissues further illustrate their contribution to cellular processes, including cell wall stability and metabolic activity (Xiang et al., 2017). The combined treatment's capacity to sustain

nutrient availability and microbial activity underscores its potential to transform soil management practices and address challenges related to declining soil fertility and environmental degradation (van Zwieten et al., 2010; Khan et al., 2024).

In addition to nutrient supply, the combination of the three amendments may have stimulated rhizosphere processes that strengthened plant–microbe interactions. The biochar provided a physical matrix protecting microorganisms from desiccation (Yang et al., 2020), while compost and compost tea acted as biological inoculants, boosting enzymatic activities such as β -glucosidase, alkaline phosphatase, and urease. These enzymes play a key role in decomposing organic residues and releasing available nutrients, thus driving the synergistic enhancement of soil fertility (Tayade et al., 2024). Moreover, biochar's influence on soil structure and moisture likely favored microbial proliferation, contributing to higher colony-forming units (CFU) of bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes (Abood, 2024).

Despite these positive outcomes, it is essential to acknowledge that CFU-based microbial counts represent only a small fraction (<1%) of the total microbial diversity, as this culture-dependent approach excludes unculturable microorganisms. Therefore, while the observed increases in microbial abundance reflect improved soil biological activity, they cannot be interpreted as a comprehensive measure of microbial diversity. Future studies using molecular techniques such as 16S rRNA and ITS sequencing will be necessary to identify the microbial taxa and functional genes promoted by these amendments.

The findings of this study have significant implications for sustainable agriculture, particularly in arid and semi-arid environments where soil degradation and nutrient loss are major challenges. The combined use of biochar, compost, and compost tea provides an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic fertilizers, reducing environmental impacts while improving soil health and crop productivity. Utilizing locally available resources, such as date palm residues for biochar production, promotes resource efficiency and supports circular economy practices. Additionally, the carbon sequestration potential of biochar contributes to climate change mitigation, aligning with global sustainability goals. The observed benefits also extend to improving soil resilience and reducing vulnerability to environmental stressors, such as drought and nutrient depletion, further enhancing the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems.

The pronounced improvements in plant biomass and leaf nutrient concentrations under the combined amendment (C + BC + CT) provide a robust physiological basis for predicting enhanced fruit yield and quality (Aegehehu et al., 2017). Vigorous vegetative growth establishes the necessary photosynthetic capacity to support fruit development (Du et al., 2018). At the same time, high tissue levels of nitrogen and potassium are critical drivers of fruit set, sugar accumulation, and overall marketable quality (Tavallali et al., 2018). Although our controlled environment study focused on the pre-fruiting stages to uncover synergistic mechanisms, these findings offer strong justification for future field research that directly quantifies fruit yield, quality, and economic viability to validate the commercial promise of this integrated strategy.

The results also highlight important implications for sustainable agriculture in arid and semi-arid regions like Morocco, where water scarcity limits tomato production. Biochar's ability to retain water and nutrients, combined with the humic substances and microbial metabolites in compost and compost tea, likely enhanced soil water-holding capacity and reduced nutrient leaching. These interactions are particularly beneficial for maintaining productivity under limited irrigation conditions common in Moroccan agriculture.

However, it is important to contextualize these findings within the scope of this study, which was conducted under controlled greenhouse conditions to isolate and elucidate the synergistic mechanisms between biochar, compost, and compost tea. Therefore, while our results demonstrate a powerful synergy with significant potential to enhance soil fertility and plant productivity, definitive agronomic validation of this combination as a full alternative to conventional RDF (Recommended Dose of Fertilizers) requires future field-scale trials. Such field studies are essential to validate these results under real-world conditions, assess long-term impacts, and include a direct side-by-side comparison with NPK fertilization. Further exploration of the microbial communities using molecular techniques and examination of the economic feasibility and scalability of this approach across diverse agricultural systems will be critical for broader adoption.

5 Conclusion

This study provides new evidence on the synergistic benefits of integrating date palm biochar, compost, and compost tea (C + BC + CT), establishing a sustainable strategy with high potential to enhance soil and plant productivity. Unlike previous studies limited to individual or dual organic amendments, this work establishes the combined use of all three as a novel approach that simultaneously improves soil biochemical functioning, microbial activity, and nutrient efficiency. The results demonstrate that this integrated amendment system strengthens the relationship between soil fertility, enzymatic processes, and plant growth, fulfilling the study's objective of linking soil biological functioning to crop performance. These enhancements translated into greater plant height, biomass accumulation, and nutrient uptake, confirming the synergistic benefits of combining biochar, compost, and compost tea. The incorporation of date palm biochar derived from locally available residues introduces a practical valorization pathway for agricultural by-products, contributing to circular economy principles and to climate-resilient agroecosystems.

Overall, this study advances current knowledge by clarifying how multiple organic inputs can act synergistically to improve soil–plant–microbe interactions. The integrated amendment strategy provides a scientifically grounded framework for reducing dependence on synthetic fertilizers while maintaining high crop productivity and improving soil health. The results provide a strong mechanistic foundation for the potential of this combination to reduce reliance on synthetic fertilizers, a claim that now

warrants validation through future field studies including direct comparison with conventional RDF. Future research should extend these findings through long-term field validation to optimize their applications across diverse agroecosystems.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

MR: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. SB: Writing – original draft. NE: Writing – original draft. AB: Writing – original draft. RB: Writing – original draft.

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Conflict of interest

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